

Stability analysis of a potential geothermal well in fractured porous media

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Abstract

Deep geothermal engineering is usually involved in fractured reservoirs with high permeability and boreholes are usually inclined to promote thermal production. Wellbore stability is particularly important in such fractured porous media. In this paper, dual-porosity and dual-permeability theories of poromechanics are employed to study the stability of a potential geothermal well using analytical solutions. The effective stresses in the rock matrix and fractures surrounding the borehole are derived and analyzed separately, where two failure criteria are applied to rock matrix and fracture, respectively. Time-dependent solutions are used to show the importance of including fracture strength in stability analysis of wellbores drilled in fracture porous media.

1. Introduction

Understanding the behavior of naturally fractured media is an indispensable task in field operations of oil and gas industry. Inclined wellbore instability issues due to the local heterogeneity of surrounding rock is of critical interest. General methods of analysis in a 3D state which is based on elastic approach proposed by Hiramatsu and Oka (1968) and Bradley (1979) do not encompass the precise mechanisms of collapse initiation. Based on their application, wellbores are buried in a deep depth in which the formation is saturated. Fractures provide low porosity-high permeability environment which induces local preference for flow and fluid-diffusion. Coupled equations which can account fluid pressure perturbation and deformation of the rock are needed. Fractured rock was usually modeled as a dual-porosity/dual-permeability porous media (Abousleiman and Nguyen 2005). The analytical solutions by Abousleiman and Nguyen (2005) accurately capture the stresses and the pore-pressure variations in rock matrix and fracture for wellbore stability analysis. However, the effect of fracture strength on wellbore stability was not considered. In this paper we employ the poromechanics/poroelastic analytical solutions of Abousleiman et al (2005) to demonstrate the importance of considering fracture strength in the borehole stability analysis of a potential geothermal well.

2. Methods and techniques

Dual-porosity concept can be described by a representative elementary volume (REV). The chosen REV as shown in Fig. 1 describes the rock matrix as well as the embedded fractures distribution. At the macroscopic level, the system is considered to consist of two separate and overlapping fluid-saturated porous media: one represents the primary porosity matrix and the other represents the secondary porosity medium fractures. Each medium is assumed to have its own poromechanical and physical properties such as elastic moduli, Biot's effective stress coefficients, and fluid mobilities. The two media communicate and may exchange fluid mass. At any REV, it is assumed that there are two separate continua, each with its own pressure field and separate constitutive laws and governing equations are considered for each region. The overall strain tensor is governed by the applied total stress tensor, and the dual pore pressure system. Pore pressures of each continua are weighted by their own Biot's constants. For the proposed REV, the stresses and strains tensors are same for both matrix and fracture under the assumption that each porous medium is homogeneous and isotropic. Here subscripts I and II refers to matrix and fracture media respectively, and α^I and α^{II} are Biot's effective stress coefficients in matrix and fracture respectively.

Fig. 1 Dual Porosity/dual permeability concept of poroelastic media. (Cowin et al 2009)

The complete analytical solution for the inclined wellbore drilled fractured-rock formation are given as follows:

$$P^I = p_0 + P^{I(2)} + P^{I(3)} \quad (1)$$

$$P^{II} = p_0 + P^{II(2)} + P^{II(3)}$$

$$\sigma_{rr} = \sigma_m - \sigma_d \cos[2(\theta - \theta_r)] - \sigma_{rr}^{(1)} - \sigma_{rr}^{(2)} - \sigma_{rr}^{(3)} \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{\theta\theta} = \sigma_m + \sigma_d \cos[2(\theta - \theta_r)] - \sigma_{\theta\theta}^{(1)} - \sigma_{\theta\theta}^{(2)} - \sigma_{\theta\theta}^{(3)} \quad (3)$$

σ_m and σ_d are mean and deviatoric stresses around the wellbore, p_0 denotes the virgin formation pore pressure before excavation which is assumed to be equal to both matrix and fracture virgin pore pressure at $r = \infty$. An example for dual porosity analytical solutions by Abousleiman and Nguyen (2005) is solved. Parameters are shown in Table 1. The solution in time is evaluated by a popular numerical inversion method which is Stehfest algorithm (Stehfest, 1970). For this case we use MATLAB to solve the Laplace equations. For the complete explanation of constitutive equations reader is referred to Abousleiman et al (2005).

Table 1 Rock-fluid properties for dual porosity modelling from Abousleiman and Nguyen (2005)

Parameter	Value
K^I, K^{II}	1100, 550 (MPa)
G^I, G^{II}	760, 380 (MPa)
K_s	27570 (MPa)
K_f	1744 (MPa)
ϕ^I, ϕ^{II}	0.14, 0.014
k^I, k^{II}	1e-19, 1e-17 (m^2)
p_0	10 (MPa)
R	0.1 (m)

Where R is radius of the well, K_s and K_f are grain bulk modulus and fluid modulus. ϕ^I and ϕ^{II} are matrix and fracture porosity, k^I and k^{II} are permeability of matrix and fracture respectively. We use different mud pressures to evaluate the response of media but as a first try it is assumed zero.

3. Results and discussions

Results of pore pressures are shown in Fig. 2. It shows that the pore pressure of fracture dissipates faster due to its high permeability.

With the dual porosity solution, the pore pressure of matrix behaves differently when comparing with the single porosity solution.

Fig. 2 Pore pressure values along radial direction

Pairs of S_p versus $\sqrt{J_2}$ can be plotted to evaluate the stability of the well. These pairs are plotted along the whole periphery of the wellbore in which θ varies from 0 to 360 degree. Stress clouds show mean shear stress which can be compared by a failure criteria like Drucker-Prager.

$$J_2 = \frac{1}{6} [(\sigma_{rr} - \sigma_{\theta\theta})^2 + (\sigma_{rr} - \sigma_{zz})^2 + (\sigma_{\theta\theta} - \sigma_{zz})^2] + \sigma_{r\theta}^2 + \sigma_{rz}^2 + \sigma_{\theta z}^2 \quad (4)$$

$$S_p = \frac{\sigma_{rr} + \sigma_{\theta\theta} + \sigma_{zz}}{3} - p^I \quad (5)$$

Fig. 3 shows the analysis which evaluate the time factor. It can be seen that as time passes, the stress cloud expands and most parts of the wellbore get failure at $t=1$ day. We replaced the pore pressure of matrix with fracture pore pressure instead to figure out the role of low pore pressure generated in fractures Eq. 6.

$$S_p = \frac{\sigma_{rr} + \sigma_{\theta\theta} + \sigma_{zz}}{3} - p^{II} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 3 Effect of different times on stress clouds at $r/R=1$ within a constant mud pressure

In addition, due to the fact that rock formations contain weak plans like bedding planes (Nguyen et al 2009), presence of fractures and bedding planes needs modified failure criteria, in this manner the amounts of ϕ and c get reduced. Blue line in Fig. 4 shows the modified failure line as to compare with fracture stress cloud. It is observed that fracture pore pressure makes a little difference but only one failure criteria based on the specific ϕ and c values for the whole formation is not enough.

Fig. 4 Matrix and fracture stress clouds

4. Conclusions

In this paper we utilize dual-porosity concept available in the literature to emphasize the importance of such model in geothermal industry or any engineering career involved with borehole excavations. Parametric studies using MATLAB code shows that radial stress and pore pressure values are highly dependent on material properties like permeability and porosities of both matrix and fracture. After the early time following excavation, the amount of pore pressure is different in fracture and matrix and this fact clearly shows the importance of using dual-porelastic solution and the necessity of considering the fracture strength.

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